

Small and Medium Enterprises (SME) Development and Economic Growth of Bangladesh: A Narrative of the Glorious 50 Years

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Abstract

The father of the Nation, Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman took significant policy measures for the improvement of the rate of literacy, reduction of poverty, industrialization, and strategic action plans for SME development. With the passage of time, the economy of Bangladesh has gradually developed through several phases, adopting strategies that resulted in a significant economic boom in the last decade. The growth of the economy can be attributed to the positive shifts - from agricultural-based to industrial-based, from input-driven to productivity-driven, and from traditional to knowledge-based-technology-orientated economy. Small and medium enterprises (SMEs) have been playing an essential role in the development of the economy of Bangladesh, and it can be claimed that it is the backbone of industrial development in the country. This paper attempts to discuss the extent to which the economy has benefited from the expansion of the SME sector and identifies the contribution of the SME Foundation in the process of uplifting and flourishing SMEs. The SME Foundation has been doing a remarkable job in this regard with continuous endeavors to facilitate innovation of new products, the introduction of new production technologies, marketing of goods and services, skills development training, advocacy, policy formulation, and linkage with national and international organizations. The study reveals that the development of the SME sector played a major role in contributing to the economic growth through providing support to the existing SMEs, creating non-traditional opportunities, generating employment, making the labor force more skilled and effective through training, enhancing labor productivity, and improving product and services quality. SMEs are accounting for 25% of the GDP of Bangladesh and 80% of total industrial jobs; and therefore, significantly has been contributing to 6% to 8% of the economic growth rate in the last decade.

Keywords: Bangladesh, Bangabandhu, economic growth, Small and Medium Enterprises (SME), SME development, SME Foundation

1. Prelude

In 1956, when the Father of the Nation, Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman was the Minister of the *Industries, commerce, labour, anti-corruption, and village administration*, established the East Pakistan Small Industry Corporation (EPSIC) to promote SMEs in the then East Pakistan, i.e., present Bangladesh. He realized the crucial importance of the role of the SME sector in the national economic development and identified the

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significance of institutional support in facilitating activities. Since the independence of Bangladesh in 1971, the economy of the country gradually progressed with steady trends. This can be identified as exceptional progress since at the time of its birth it has a devastating economic condition due to the war of independence, the legacy of discriminated economic treatment from the then Pakistan, and insignificant industrial development in this part. This progress has been possible as there has been a visible increase in the gross domestic product (GDP) over the last 50 years. The average GDP growth rate was 2-3% in the 1970s, around 3.5% in the 1980s, 4.5-5% in the 1990s, and more than 6% over the first decade of the 21st century (Helal and Hossain, 2013). GDP growth rate was 8.2% in 2019 and 5.2% in 2020, and the forecasted GDP growth rate of 2021 is 6.8% and 2022 is 7.2% (ADB, 2021).

In Bangladesh, women constitute roughly half of the population. So, the development processes of the country can be accelerated ensuring their active participation. Given the economic and social contribution made by the entrepreneurial programs, it is significant to understand the factors that lead to the success of women-owned businesses. An understanding of these factors may result in measures that could reduce the failure of these businesses.

Bangladesh reached the 'lower-middle-income status' in 2015 and is on track to graduate from the UN's Least Developed Countries (LDC) list in 2026; and the poverty level declined from 44% in 1991 to 15% in 2016 (World Bank, 2021a). The country has done a phenomenal improvement in agriculture, industrial sectors, garments, manufacturing, and services. SMEs are associated in every way with all these booming sectors. In most economies, SMEs play a major role and are particularly important for developing countries (World Bank, 2021b). It is evident that SMEs influence a flourishing economy. Positive economic impacts can be in the form of increased employment and earning opportunities, enhanced standard of living, increased investments, infrastructural development, and new business linkages and opportunities (Rahman, 2010). Emphasis is given on the necessity of adequate financial and institutional supports to promote SMEs as it is often identified that institutional support is less for them compared to that of large-scale investments, although their prospects are high (ibid).

This paper attempts to unfold the achievements of Bangladesh over the last 50 years since its independence. It provides an overview of the conditions and development of SMEs in Bangladesh and discusses their contributions to the economy. It identifies the plans and policies the government of Bangladesh (GoB) and the related institutions have been adopting to enable the development of SMEs and to boost local consumptions and

exports. The paper is structured with a prelude at first, the analysis of literature on the role of small and medium entrepreneurs on the economic development of Bangladesh is presented at second, identification of major objectives at third, discussion on methodology at the fourth, discussion on the evolution of SMEs at fifth, discussion on the evolution of SME Foundation at sixth, analysis of the current situation at seventh, and recommendations and conclusion at last.

2. Context of the Economic Development of Bangladesh

The theoretical framework of the economic development of Bangladesh over the last 50 years might be contextualized based on the review of literature on the roles of the small and medium entrepreneurs. The significant role of entrepreneurs in the process of economic development is described by W. W. Rostow while exploring the relationships between entrepreneurship development and economic growth (Shaper, 1971; Rostow, 1971). The five stages of growth include the traditional society, the preconditions for take-off, the take-off, the drive to maturity, and the age of high mass-consumption (Rostow, 1959 and 1990). The process of economic growth centers around the theory that over a period of two or three decades the economy and the society start transforming in such a way that economic growth becomes an obvious outcome, and this transformation is usually identified as the take-off (Rostow, 1971). This theory somewhat tallies with the progression of economic growth of Bangladesh and explains the experiences of the shifts among the self-sustained stages of economic growth. Early research (Khondkar, 1992) claimed that entrepreneurship is an essential factor to national wealth-building; therefore, Bangladesh needs the talent, ability, and drive of the entrepreneurs to utilize the resources to transform into profitable enterprises required for industrialization and economic development. A country's prosperity depends on its ability to produce useful products and services and to spread the benefits to the mass people (ibid). Although entrepreneurs usually vary in demographic profiles, it is often claimed that their success can be attributed to the common traits of commitment (Rahman and Alam, 2018).

Global poverty reduction has been associated with economic marginalization of the least developed areas and emphasis is given on maintaining political stability, taking poverty reduction initiatives, and regularly assessing poverty reduction initiatives to augment the resilience capacity of poverty alleviation and to foster economic development (Li *et al.*, 2021). In Bangladesh, the rate of poverty reduction exhibits a downtrend, however, it is not compatible with the high growth rate of the GDP; and inequality is also increasing at a fast pace (Titumir, 2021). Livani (2021) identified that economic growth in Bangladesh has been mainly constrained by trade barriers and a lack of women's economic

empowerment and suggested that increased international trade and more liberalized trade participation and ensuring equal gains for women can be an effective tool for economic growth and poverty reduction. Anti-poverty interventions are supposed to give proper attention to gender issues, sustainability, research and development (R&D), and access to information (Ahmed *et al*, 2011).

The basic tool for achieving growth is industrialization, as it creates jobs and reduces unemployment. It creates opportunities for the population to participate in skilled activities by transforming them into human resources and assets for the country. Worldwide, SMEs are one of the major contributors to job creation and global economic development as they represent about 90% of the businesses and offer more than 50% of the employment opportunities (World Bank, 2021b). In emerging economies, SMEs are contributing about 40% of the GDP and creating 7 out of 10 jobs; however, access to finance is a key constraint to their growth (*ibid*). The following Table 1 presents the sector-wise percentage contributions to the GDP of Bangladesh over the last 50 years.

Table1. Sector-wise Contribution to GDP

Year	Agriculture (%)	Industry (%)	Services (%)
1972-1973	49.76	9.00	36.46
1980-1981	46.58	11.08	42.34
1990-1991	29.23	21.04	49.72
2000-2001	25.03	26.20	48.77
2010-2011	18.00	27.38	54.61
2019-2020	13.48	30.82	55.71

Source: BBS, 2021, 2017, and 2010.

One study found that Bangladesh Small and Cottage Industries Corporation (BSCIC) has a significant role in industrial expansion and poverty reduction in Bangladesh and it significantly influences household consumption and poverty reduction. A 1% increase in income from BSCIC will increase the yearly household consumption by 0.73%, whereas it is only 0.36% in the case of non-BSCIC income (Haider *et al.*, 2015). To achieve the Millennium Development Goals and the South Asia Development Goals, Bangladesh needs to adopt appropriate policies and strategies. BSCIC, The SME Foundation, the National Association of Small Cottage Industries of Bangladesh (NASCIB), and Bangladesh Women's Chamber of Commerce and Industry are the key partners to achieve the goals.

Despite SMEs in Bangladesh account for 25% of the total labor force, this sector gets limited assistance from support service providers and faces constraints like lack of credit facilities, market access, modern technology, and business information (Alam and Ullah, 2006). It is found that for a long time, fair trade practices have been introduced through the ECOTA Forum, which is a national networking body of non-government organizations (NGOs) and SMEs engaged in small-scale cottage industry-based exports, to ensure better coordination for better marketing and linking with the market abroad to ensure fair price to the traders and to help them develop related skills (Rahman, 2002). It is identified that lack of support, resources, finance, and access to entrepreneurial learning work as barriers to self-employment; and funded support for their entrepreneurial learning along with undergraduate and postgraduate level entrepreneurship course provisions are required (Edwards and Muir, 2005). There exists a limitation for SMEs' access to international trade and it is caused by a lack of required technological know-how and a lack of knowledge about the opportunities offered by foreign markets (Damin, 2021).

In the SME sector, many opportunities are either left untapped or partially utilized with less efficiency and effectiveness due to the lack of formal financial assistance in terms of loans, leasing, and others. Both GoB and private sector banks usually do not offer adequate financial assistance to facilitate SME development. If they offer loan packages for the SME sector, then existing leakage may get reduced, and more business initiatives will get consistent financing, resulting in a better earning for the people (Rahman, 2010). Nowadays, information and communication technology (ICT) is considered an inseparable concept for economic development and if an adaptive and sustainable technology framework can be developed by efficiently utilizing labor forces then we can develop our economy further (Muzareba and Rahman, 2014). During this COVID-19 pandemic and in the changing environment of the new normal, it has been particularly realized that ICT can contribute to the progression of all sorts of economic activities. A recent study has emphasized the use of ICT for development (ICT4D) in Bangladesh and identified that internet-based entrepreneurs often make considerable economic gains though that sometimes come with a few social consequences which the culture has to deal with (Muzareba, 2021).

A significant number of women entrepreneurs are contributing to the SMEs of Bangladesh through their performance, and they were found to be playing significant roles in reducing poverty and unemployment (Rahman *et al.*, 2020). However, most of them are constrained by the lack of a starter capital, shortage of collateral, limited access to the capital market, lack of market access, related theoretical knowledge, and ICT skilled manpower (*ibid*). Micro-finance institutions (MFIs), such as the Grameen Bank

and BRAC have been contributing through their credit programs to assisting disadvantaged rural women, and credit with a social development approach is claimed to be more likely to achieve the goal of poverty reduction (Khondkar, 1998). Although microcredits impact the productivity of its clients and contribute to poverty reductions, possibilities of alternative policy options should also be considered (Islam, 2016).

3. Objectives

The broad objective of the paper is to grasp the roles of the development of SMEs in the economic growth of Bangladesh over the last 50 years. The specific objectives are outlined below.

- i. To address how the five-year plans of the GoB led the development in the SME sector.
- ii. To examine the development challenges and prospects of the sector.
- iii. To examine the roles of SMEs as well as their contribution to the economy.
- iv. To analyze the contribution of SME Foundation to the SME sector.

4. Methodology

This study uses a qualitative research approach and involves analyses of primary and secondary data. To achieve the objectives of the study, it uses textual analysis and content analysis. Therefore, the methodology used in this study included identification, analysis, and examination of relevant documents and communication artifacts to draw interpretations to identify patterns in research issues in a replicable and systematic manner. It is a widely accepted and used methodology that uses the available data and text to gain information related to the problem at hand (Krippendorff, 2018; Dumay and Cai, 2015). The textual examination provided pieces of evidence that were in written, spoken, and/or visual message forms which assisted to comprehend the phenomena. Facts were driven based on the contents and meanings of the texts of their discourse and structure (Stemler, 2015; Fursich, 2009). Books, articles published in quality journals, research papers, annual reports, and audio-visual data related to the economic growth of Bangladesh and its relation to the SME sector are considered as the contents. Primary and secondary data were collected from different sources including the Asian Development Bank (ADB), United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), World Bank, Bangladesh Bank, Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics (BBS), and SME Foundation. The discussion and discourses throughout the paper have developed analytical interpretations and resulted in probable theoretical outcomes and policy implications.

5. Evolution of SMEs in Bangladesh

After the dreadful war of independence, SMEs started to play an important role during the early years of 1972-1975 to recover the country's economy. Private sectors were

motivated to participate in the national development with the philosophy of social justice and economy of equality to make the country self-reliant and self-sustained. It was realized that as women and youths form a significant portion of the population, their active participation was required to accelerate economic activities. To achieve that, the GoB gradually privatized the nationalized industries, promoted the free market concept of economy, took steps for development activities in rural and suburban areas, and created opportunities for self-employment through making supportive arrangements for small, medium, and cottage industries. This flow of privatization matches with what Humphrey (2019) also claimed that privatization allowed the traditional society to cope with modernization and facilitated economic growth. GoB could thus influence human resource developments and ensure easing of the economic growth by doing these.

In 1972, the Bangladesh Planning Commission was formed which prepared the development plans for the socio-economic development of the country. The development philosophy at that moment was to establish equality and social justice. The First Five Year Plan (1973-1978) was formulated during the regime of the Father of the Nation, Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman, and it reflected his philosophy of putting pivotal emphasis on self-reliance of the country. It gave special attention to agriculture and small and cottage industries. At that time, the father of the nation dreamed of a vision that SMEs can play a major role in creating an egalitarian society that is free from all forms of exploitation in Bangladesh (Sobhan, 2021). It is now observed that SMEs are playing a major role in increasing employment by bringing economic growth and enhancing job equality. In the beginning, there was the dominance of public ownership of industry and public control of a large part of foreign trade (Muhith, 1993). During the implementation of the new industrial policy of 1972, the number of private sectors increased, and some selected public sectors were decentralized. For industrial development, 650 industrial enterprises were converted into private ownership entities where about 50% were weak industries earlier. In that situation, a new strategy was introduced where private and foreign direct investments (FDI) were given more emphasis (BIDS, 1990). These initiatives created opportunities for export-oriented labor-intensive industries. The employment of women in public and private sectors increased due to the extension of education and training, and to accelerate it further there was a quota for them in overall employment. The youth also have been offered opportunities for technical training to form enterprises and build various economic infrastructures.

Consecutive national five-year plans emphasized the continuation of the economic development initiatives to gradually increase the rate of economic growth. To ensure the progress of the women and the youth, some human development training programs were

also taken. Women's education was particularly emphasized. The country has been progressing significantly in terms of the human development index (HDI) as it is ranked at 133 among 156 associated countries with an HDI of 0.632 (UNDP, 2020). Employment opportunity was enhanced through the development of new entrepreneurs, and sub-contracting to SMEs by the large and medium enterprises. Agro-based and export-oriented industries were also encouraged in a similar manner. Gradually, the policymakers realized the importance of this sector and eventually tried to create a supportive environment for the progress of the sector, mainly through financing, policy reforms, skill development training, and providing institutional support.

6. Evolution of SME Foundation

At first, the SME sector received a formal institutional focus through the formation of East Pakistan Small Industries Corporation (EPSIC) in 1956, and after the independence that institution became BSCIC. In 2008, SME Foundation was established as a company, limited by guarantee and licensed under section 28 of the Companies Act 1994 by the GoB to implement and support small and medium ventures (SME Foundation, 2021). SME Foundation was formed to implement the government's policies and strategies and facilitate the private organizations in their initiatives to accelerate the performance of SMEs. The vision of the SME Foundation is to nurture SMEs to contribute to social progress through reducing social inequality, decreasing poverty, increasing the rate of employment, and making impacts on economic growth. The mission is to provide proper guidance for promoting the growth of SMEs in the case of both the productive and service-oriented enterprises to encounter the challenges of the free-market economy and globalization (SME Foundation, 2020). The goals of the foundation are to develop SMEs by encouraging, motivating, and organizing entrepreneurs through planning, developing, capacity building, awareness-raising, evaluating, and undertaking advocacy programs.

In line with the mission and vision, the SME Foundation has been accomplishing various programs organized for the development of the SME sector. It is assisting the implementation of SME policies adopted by GoB. The major responsibility of the foundation is to aid the implementation of government-guided development policies related to revenue and financial advice, quality assurance of SME products, skill development strategies, technopreneurship development, making information accessible through web portals, international technology exchange programs, and virtual platform.

Significant research and policy advocacy supports are also provided by the foundation. The main goal of the research and policy advocacy is to support the activities related to forming an SME-friendly environment for efficient business management. The SME

Foundation constitutes the detailed procedures with updated information and data for the formulation of SME-related policies and strategies to overcome the existing regulatory barriers in the country. The foundation regularly undertakes R&D initiatives to assist the formulation of short-term, long-term, and contextual plans for SME development. The database of the web portal of this foundation provides detailed information, which is regularly updated to ensure access to current information about SME entrepreneurs and all other stakeholders.

In 2013, SME Foundation identified 177 clusters in the country and started cluster-based activities. The main goal was cluster development through enhancing the personal skills, management skills, and technical skills of the entrepreneurs and employees. Typically, a cluster is a concentration of enterprises producing similar products or services and is situated in geographical proximity, and having common strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats (SME Foundation, 2021). In Bangladesh, the key criteria to define SME clusters are similarity and homogeneity of products and services, enterprises produce goods and services under respective units, the number of units are 50 or above, there exists geographical proximity of the units, and units are scattered over an area of three-to-five-kilometer radius. For instance, in the Bogra region, there are about 4,000 industrial units of SMEs operating in seven clusters (Moazzemet *al.*, 2016).

Finance and credit services are offered by the Finance and Credit Services department of the foundation under the Credit Wholesale program. These loans are provided through selected banks and non-banking financial institutions, as no loan is provided directly from the foundation. Loan fairs, banker-entrepreneur conferences, seminars, loan-related matchmaking, training of bankers, and communication through media coverage are organized on regular basis in various districts of the country to enhance awareness about the increased financing opportunities in the SME sector. Notably, collateral-free loans at single-digit interest rates are provided to the SME under the clusters all over Bangladesh and the loan recovery rate is 100% (SME Foundation, 2021). During this COVID-19 pandemic, the government allocated BDT100 crore as a stimulus package for the SME sector and this amount has been distributed fully within the targeted time frame.

The SME Foundation organizes various skills development initiatives which include diverse training programs to enhance the skills of existing entrepreneurs and to facilitate the creation of new entrepreneurs. It also organizes training programs in collaboration with various training institutes and other SME-related associations. Training activities focus on entrepreneurship development, SME cluster-based skills development, technology and ICT, training of trainers, productivity, product quality improvement, financial

management, and marketing. Regarding the integration of contemporary technological developments with entrepreneurial initiatives, the foundation organizes regular events on the adaptation and use of modern technology, borrowing and adopting advanced foreign technologies, green technology, and efficient use of energy. It offers training and assistance regarding product and services compliance and related certification. Therefore, it is also assisting enhancement of product quality and acquiring quality certification. The foundation provides supports related to product quality assurance and quality certification, for instance, ISO-9000 and ISO-14000 are provided to the SMEs. Development of advanced quality designs and packaging systems are also supported.

Another important role of the SME Foundation relates to women's entrepreneurship development. It encourages, supports, and ensures the inclusion of women entrepreneurs in the mainstream of the development process. It thus contributes to the empowerment of women through some remarkable activities such as the institutional capacity building of women entrepreneurs, chambers, and trade bodies. A significant contribution is made through enhancing policy advocacy in creating women entrepreneur-friendly environment and uplifting the networks and platforms connecting women from all corners of Bangladesh and enabling their voices raised and heard.

Business support services are also provided by the SME foundation, such as promotion and market expansion of the SME products, the establishment of interconnections between consumers and entrepreneurs, guidance, making information and data on new business creation and management available through the advisory service center, publication, and distribution of business information in the form of manual, SME product fair, and national SME entrepreneur award competition. During this COVID-19 pandemic, the SME Foundation started an e-commerce site to support the entrepreneurs to overcome the challenges of selling their products and services through traditional channels.

7. Analysis of the Current Situation

Bangladesh is simultaneously experiencing both urbanization and industrialization (Chen *et al*, 2014). The expansion and performance of small and medium-scale manufacturing industries are associated with the proximity to river or water bodies and roads, and the country being riverine can explain that reality to a degree (Hassan *et al*, 2020). Although Bangladesh achieved a steady economic growth rate from 6% to 8% during the last decade, however, due to the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic the GDP growth rate became 5.24% in 2019-2020, compared to 8.15% in 2018-2019 (GoB, 2020). This industrial growth is mainly attributed to the growing numbers of SMEs, as around 80% of the employment in the industrial sector is in the SMEs (Hassan *et al*, 2020; GoB, 2017).

Although agriculture is a vast source of employment in this agrarian economy, the industrial sector is enabling the economic boost. The industrial sector contributes about 33% of the GDP and has grown by over 11% in 2016–2017 (GoB, 2017; CPD, 2018). There has been a significant increase in the per capita GDP of Bangladesh; it was USD 94.38 in 1972 and it became USD 1968.79 in 2020 (World Bank, 2021c). A good amount of export earnings is coming from the manufacturing sector. The backbone of this economic growth is the ready-made garment (RMG) sector. FDI flow to Bangladesh was USD 3.6 billion in 2018 and USD 1.6 billion in 2019; and the share in the global apparel market was 6.3% for Bangladesh in 2020 (Rahman, 2021). In 2020, the share of RMG exports was approximately 83% of the total exports and this was an increase from 2011 when it was 78.15% (Statista, 2021). RMG factories are associated with small factories or businesses through sub-contracting where SMEs are involved with the manufacturing of different types of garment accessories. Thus, the growth of the RMG sector also contributes to the creation of a supply chain network between the RMG and the SME sectors.

In the last 50 years, Bangladeshi expatriates sent more than USD 231 billion in remittances (The Business Standard, 2021). Remittances from migrants change the shape of GDP and play a significant role in the SME sector. USD 11.8 million was remitted in 1974-1975 which rose to USD 350 million in 1980-1981, USD 750 million in 1990-1991, and USD 21.75 billion in 2019-2020 to Bangladesh (Khan and Sultana, 2021). Although most of the remitted money is sent through legit channels, some portion of the money is remitted through illegal channels, but there has always been an increasing influx of inward remittance (Barkat *et al.*, 2014). Even during this COVID-19 pandemic, remittance inflow showed about 11% growth in 2019-2020 and it became a record high USD 24.77 billion in 2020-2021 with a 36% growth (Bangladesh Bank, 2021; The Business Standard, 2020). Families of around eight to ten million migrants live in rural areas. A significant portion of these vast remittances is spent on productive investments activities there. In addition to that, significant growth in manufacturing activities in the industrial sectors such as textile, leather, pharmaceuticals, light engineering, plastics, furniture, agricultural processing, and shipbuilding are evidenced in the country.

8. Recommendations and Conclusion

Bangladesh is an overpopulated country with the predominance of a domestic market of 160 million people and thus GoB needs to motivate the people to use domestic products to contribute to economic growth through enhancing demand for local products. During any natural hazards such as this COVID-19 pandemic, people ought to understand the importance of the domestic market to ensure continuity of the economic cycle. Policymakers should encourage entrepreneurs to participate in regional and national level

fairs, more importantly in online fairs on digital platforms. Steps can be taken to increase the number of visitors and buyers in all online fairs. Large industries should come forward to purchase products from SMEs at the local and national levels. Small and medium entrepreneurs should update their business plans to bring on-demand products such as personal protective equipment (PPE), masks, hand sanitizers, gloves, and so on. Proper guidance should be developed to find alternative markets for selling respective products. Government support should be extended towards entrepreneurs in the areas of production, transportation, marketing, and sales in the coming days. SMEs can be categorized based on employment size and the technology used in the organization, to facilitate contextual policy and infrastructural supports. There should be effective partnerships with different financial institutions to ensure the necessary funds for SMEs. In addition to backward and forward linkages, assistance and supports to entrepreneurs could be provided regarding other important issues such as connectivity to the global market, strong social networking, and effective and efficient subcontracting.

Although there has been tremendous advancement in the SME sector, SMEs in Bangladesh are still facing a few domestic and global challenges in achieving economies of scale and competing globally. Common challenges include a lack of working capital, a lack of technological capabilities, a low level of related ICT penetration, a limited number of skilled human resources, and a lack of regular R&D activities, dependency on the domestic market, severe competition in the global market, and red tapes of bureaucracy. These findings suggest that there are ample scopes for future endeavors for furthering SME initiatives. Therefore, a positive first step might be formulating a workable framework in the digital platform for SMEs to overcome the challenges.

SMEs can play a major role in creating an egalitarian society in Bangladesh, according to the dream of the father of the Nation, Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman. SMEs are playing a significant role to increase employment, production, and ensure economic growth. The present government has given priority to the SME sector considering it as a driving force for economic development. The SME Foundation has been significantly contributing by supporting policy advocacy, technical assistance, proficiency, and skills development training, promotions, sales-matchmaking, and marketing of the new products. Bangladesh has so far been making notable economic progress every year. However, because of weak infrastructure and a lack of a fully supportive business environment, the industrial base of the country has not yet been able to stand on a solid base. Considering these challenges, appropriate smarter strategies need to be adopted so that the SME sector can get a supportive environment that will help to create production networks for large industries. For grooming the SME sector, proper arrangements and

regular monitoring of their activities are vital. The future economic growth of Bangladesh depends on the SME sector and the government's continual assistance and instructions are imperative in this regard. Some of the suggestions are put forward in the list below for future policy implications.

- SME development is a high priority to create new jobs to absorb the growing workforce of Bangladesh and therefore deserves more focused primacy attention from the key stakeholders.
- The education system of the country must be geared towards supplying a workforce that can efficiently contribute to the labor market. In addition to the existing education platform, vocational and technical training need to be expanded further.
- Analysis of the context evidences the necessity for the training of entrepreneurs involved in SMEs, in order to ensure their further development. The development of women entrepreneurs, who are involved in SMEs, through appropriate training is an integral part of the positive force required for the economic development of Bangladesh.
- Special attention should be given to the frequently overlooked issues such as poor communication, lack of networking, unfavorable rules and regulations, unfriendly business environment, societal resistance, and lack of training and development.
- Further scope for value addition by identifying new possibilities in the SME sector and ensuring curation and patronization of related innovations need to be focused on to align Bangladesh with the fourth industrial revolution.
- Assistance in the form of requirements can be offered to micro and small enterprises for up-gradation to the respective next level.
- Recognition and inclusion of informal SMEs might significantly increase the contributions of the SME sector to the economic development of Bangladesh.
- A workable framework in the digital platform, utilizing the benefits of ICT adoption for SMEs, needs to be formulated to overcome the existing related challenges and to enable the economy to encounter the new challenges posed by the post-pandemic new normal realities.

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